

MOTM Journal Publication Handbook

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Overview

This document explains how to use the Meeting of the Minds Journal Template to produce PDF proofs for the journal.

The basic process requires you to

1. Open the [MotM Word Template](#);
2. Open the article you want to format;
3. Select all the text in the article you want to format;
4. Paste it into the open template¹;
5. Save it under a new name;
6. Apply styles;
7. Create PDF;
8. Send proofs to author;
9. Make final corrections;
10. Go to the Zenodo site and start an upload, pre-registering a DOI;
11. Copy the DOI from the Zenodo site into the Article's properties in Word (Custom > Document Number);
12. Make and check final PDF of article;
13. Fill in the Zenodo form with the relevant metadata;
14. Save the metadata and upload the file;
15. Publish.

¹ You can't just attach the template, as attaching a template does not affect headers and footers.

Required material and software

- A recent version of Word
- The article you want to format
- The Meeting of the Minds Template

Preparing the Proofs

1. Open the documents
 - a. Open [template](#)
 - b. open article you wish to format
2. Copy the content of the article you wish to format into the open template
 - a. Select everything in the article (CTL+A),
 - b. copy, and paste the highlighted text into the open template
3. Save the open template as a word document under a new name
 - a. **File>Save As**
 - b. Choose “Word Document (*.docx)”
 - c. Construct a new name using the following format: **lastName-YYYY-MM-DD**
(where lastName = the Author’s last name; YYYY = The year in digits [e.g. 2017]; MM and DD = Month and Year in 2 digits [e.g. 12-03]).
4. Modify the document properties
 - a. Open advanced properties (File>Info>Properties>Advanced Properties)

- b. On the Summary tab, paste the article title (format: Title Case) and author name (format: first-name last-name) into the space provided

The screenshot shows the 'Esau formatted (1) Properties' dialog box with the 'Summary' tab selected. The 'Title' field is populated with 'e Dion's Apology for Canadian Military Export Controls' and the 'Author' field is populated with 'Paul Esau'. Other fields like Subject, Manager, Company, Category, Keywords, Comments, and Hyperlink base are empty. The 'Template' is set to 'CJNS GSA template' and there is an unchecked checkbox for 'Save Thumbnails for All Word Documents'.

- c. On the Custom tab, select "Document Number" and then paste the following DOI place holder into the value field: **10.5281/zenodo.xxxxxx**

The screenshot shows the 'Esau formatted (1) Properties' dialog box with the 'Custom' tab selected. The 'Name' dropdown menu is open, showing options like Department, Destination, Disposition, Division, Document number, and Editor. 'Document number' is selected. The 'Type' is set to 'Text' and the 'Value' field contains '10.5281/zenodo.xxxxxx'. There are 'Modify' and 'Delete' buttons next to the Name dropdown. A 'Link to content' checkbox is unchecked. A table at the bottom shows the current custom property:

Name	Value	Type
Documen...	10.5281/ze...	Text

5. If there are footnotes in the document, convert them temporarily to endnotes

- a. References > Footnote > “Expand Icon”

- b. Convert Button > Convert all footnotes to endnotes > OK Button

6. On new line(s) after the title in the main document, add the colophon (each item on a separate line):
- Author name** (First-name Last-Name)
 - Department or Programme** (Optional)

c. **Institution** (Usually “University of Lethbridge”) (Optional)

7. [Use Search and replace](#) to remove tabs:

- a. CTL+H (advanced search and replace)
- b. Ensure cursor is in the “Search” field
- c. Click on the “Special” button (if special is not visible, click on “More” then “Special”)
- d. Select “Tab Character”

- e. Leave the replace box blank
 - f. Click “Replace all”
8. Apply block-level (i.e. “paragraph-level”) styles throughout the document
- a. Turn on “Reveal codes”

- i. Home > “Pilcrow” (¶) button

- b. For every block that ends in a Pilcrow
- i. Place the cursor somewhere in the main body (not inside a section with special character formatting like italics in a section that is normally not italics). ***Do not highlight any text in the section, just place the cursor inside the section.***
 - ii. From the style ribbon (under the Home tab) click on the correct style to apply to the section (when you hold the cursor over the styles, the text reformats to show you what it will look like; clicking on the style applies the choice).

Common choices include:

1. **Article Title MotM** (used for the main title of the article only)
 2. **Byline MotM** (used for the colophon)
 3. **Text Body MotM** (used for the first paragraph of the article, and for the first paragraph immediately after headings and block quotes)
 4. **Text Body Indent MotM** (used for all other paragraphs)
 5. **Block Quote MotM** (used for Block Quotations)
 6. **Header MotM** (used for subheaders in the article)
 7. **Image Caption MotM** (used for captions)
 8. **Reference MotM** (used for bibliographic references)
 9. **Bullet list MotM** (for bulleted lists; you can also use this for numbered lists, just change the bullet button to the numbered list button)
 10. **Footnote Body MotM** (used for footnotes/endnotes).
9. Ensure that the following paragraphs have a flush-left first line (i.e. no indent) and are styled using **Text Body MotM** style (and *not* **Text Body Indent MotM**):
- a. The first paragraph of the article or any discrete sections
 - b. The first paragraph after any heading
 - c. The first paragraph after a block quotation or image/caption
10. Make sure that there are no blank lines before or after Block Quotations
- a. The **Block Quotation MotM** style separates the quotation from the preceding text by the equivalent of 1 line (about 10 pt);
 - b. **Text Body MotM** separates the first line of a paragraph by about the same amount.
11. Apply **Footnote Body MotM** to each endnote

- a. Place the cursor inside the endnote (do not select text in the endnote, and ensure that you are not in a section of italics)
- b. From the Style ribbon under Home, select **Footnote Body MotM**.
- c. Examine the endnote for text that does not fit the new style (e.g. is a different font face or size). If you see any:
 - i. highlight the text that is not correctly formatted
 - ii. On the Home tab, click on the “Clear all Formatting” button

12. Convert Endnotes back to Footnotes
 - a. (Reverse what you did to convert footnotes to endnotes)
13. Check that all footnote markers (in the main body and in the footnotes) are
 - a. Flush against the preceding punctuation or text (i.e. not separated by a space from the preceding text)
 - b. Superscript
 - i. If the footnote markers are not superscript in both places, you can do a global search and replace for them:
 1. CTL+H to open advanced search and replace
 2. In the search field: **^f**
 3. In the replace field: **^&**
 4. Click on the “format” button
 5. Choose “Font”

6. Ensure that the “Superscript” check box has a checkmark in it and click “OK”

7. “Replace All”

14. Add standard section headers (if they are not present); in each case use the **Header MotM** style to format them:

- a. **Abstract** (if there is an abstract)

- i. Note: if the article has an abstract, then the first paragraph of the main body of the text must also be preceded by a header (i.e. there must be a header between the abstract and the main body of the article).
 1. If the article has a sub-head before the first paragraph of the main body, use the author’s subtitle.
 2. If it does not, repeat the main title of the article (style using **Header MotM**) between the Abstract and the first paragraph of the article (this is APA recommended style)

- b. **Works Cited**

- i. Note: if the author has a different title for the reference section (e.g. “References” or similar), our practice is to accept the author’s title, except in the case of “Bibliography,” which should only be accepted if the author insists.

15. Add If there is not a header before the reference section, use “Works Cited” formatted using the **Header MotM** style

16. Check that the header is properly formatted and aligned on even and odd pages (except for page 1)

- a. The “pipe” character (| or “vertical line”) should line up with the left edge of the main body text on verso (even number) pages and with the right edge on recto

(odd number pages)

- i. If it is not properly aligned, click in the header and use the cursor to drag the # button in the ruler bar back and forth until it is properly aligned. (If the ruler bar is not visible, you can turn it on under the “View” tab).
- b. Check that the page numbers are arabic and start with page 1
 - i. If there is no page number,
 1. Insert > Page Number > Current Position > Plain Number

- ii. If the number is not Arabic or the article does not start at page 1

1. Insert > Page Number > Format Page Numbers

- c. Check that the title is not running over the margin on even numbered pages (i.e. the verso)
 - i. If it is, then you need to shorten the field box for the title:
 1. Click somewhere in the title in the header
 2. Slide the cursor past the edge of the box until you see the horizontal resize icon appear (i.e.)
 3. Slide the border to the left until the title fits correctly in the space. This truncates the title: some text drops onto the next line, but is invisible. Stop truncating when you hit a short title that makes sense.
17. Use Search and Replace to replace all double and single quotation marks and apostrophes with “Smart quotes” (i.e. “ ”, and ‘ ’)
 - a. Open the advanced search and replace dialogue using CTL+H
 - b. In both the search and replace fields, type " (i.e. a straight quotation mark)
 - c. Click on “Replace all”
 - d. Repeat for ' (straight apostrophe).
18. Use Search and Replace to make sure double hyphens (--) are replaced by em-dashes (—). Our house style is to have no spaces between the preceding or following word and an em-dash. So something like this -- an example where the double hyphen has a space on each side -- should be replaced by this— an em-dash that touches the preceding and following words).
19. Check the author name, title, etc. in the citation and copyright information in the first page footer is correct
 - a. If there are problems, these need to be fixed in the document properties.
20. Turn on Line Number:

- a. Layout > Line Numbers > Continuous

21. Save as PDF with the same file name as the Word document (i.e. **lastName-YYYY-MM-DD**): File > Save As > *.pdf
22. Open PDF and review for obvious problems
23. When the proofs are ready send them to the author
 - a. Ask the author to use line or footnote numbers when indicating changes.

Correcting the Proofs and preparing the Final Version

1. Open the Word file associated with the proofs (i.e. **lastName-YYYY-MM-DD.docx**)
2. Save it under a new name: **lastname-Final-YYYY-MM-DD.docx**
3. Implement the changes requested by the author. Use the line numbers to find the passages they are referring to.
4. Turn off Line Numbers:

- a. Layout > Line Numbers > None

2. Go to <http://zenodo.org>
3. Select "Upload" from the top menu bar, and log in or "sign up" if asked
4. Select "New Upload" (Green button)
5. Under "Basic Information" you will find a DOI field.
 - a. Click on "Pre-Reserve DOI" and copy the number that shows up in the DOI field afterwards (it will look something like this: **10.5281/zenodo.376789**)
6. In the Proofs (i.e. the Word file for the article), past this number in File > Properties > Advanced Properties > Custom > Document Number > Value

7. When you click OK, this number should now show up on the first page footer, after the journal title

Paul Esau. 2017. "Selling Out to the Saudis: A Historical Analysis of Stephane Dion's Apology for Canadian Military Export Controls." *Meeting of the Minds Graduate Student Journal* (<http://ulgsajournal.com>). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.376789.
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8. Save the file as a PDF using the same name you used for the word document (i.e. lastname-Final-YYYY-MM-DD.pdf). This is the final publication form of the document, so take a last look that nothing is wrong with it. **It cannot be changed after it is uploaded.**
9. In the Zenodo Upload page, enter all the bibliographic information you can in the "Basic Information" section:
 - a. **Publication type:** "Journal article"
 - b. **Digital Object Identifier:** Should be filled in if you selected "Pre-reserve DOI" If it isn't click on the "Pre-reserve DOI button now to fill it in.
 - c. **Title:** Copy the complete article title from the file
 - d. **Authors:** "Lastname, Firstname" and the affiliation information from the colophon. For affiliation use the format: **Department/Programme, Institution**. If there is more than one author, add new boxes for additional authors by clicking on the "+ Add another author" link directly under the text box. You can use the two triangles icon at the right hand side to change the order of the authors after you have entered them.
 - e. **Description:** Paste the Abstract here. If there is no abstract, paste the first few paragraphs--enough to explain the context of the article.
 - f. **Keywords:** If the author has supplied keywords, paste them here.
 - g. **Access right:** Select **Open Access**.
 - h. **Licence:** Select **Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0**
 - i. **Communities:** Start typing **Meeting** and our journal name should come up.
 - j. **Related/alternate identifiers:** Click on the title to expand this section and paste the Journal URL (<http://ulgsajournal.com>) into the first box
 - k. **Journal:** Click on the title to expand this section:
 - i. **Journal Title:** Meeting of the Minds Graduate Student Journal
 - ii. **Volume:** The correct volume
10. **SAVE the information using the Save** button at the end of the page.
11. Go back to the top of the page and Click "Choose files"
12. Navigate to the PDF you made of the final version. Upload this.
13. Once it is uploaded, click "Save" again. Then "Publish."
14. You should now be able to see the article in Zenodo.
15. Once the file is uploaded, get the link to the PDF and use this to construct the Landing page for the article in Wordpress.